

Stochastic Model Comparison Methods with Highly Correlated Latent Traits

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Correlated Latent Traits

- Many cognitive based latent traits are highly correlated
- Situated Decision-making: clinical knowledge and skills may be highly correlated with context specific clinical decision-making
- When sets of observations are highly correlated, factor analytic solutions have difficulty separating them.

Simulation Study

Bidimensional IRT

Bayesian Estimation

Maximum Likelihood Estimation

Pseudo Bayes Factor

Implications

- Stochastic vs Deterministic estimation
 - Both methods recovered parameters well
 - Parameter estimates highly correlated ~ .99
 - Near perfect model selection ~ .99
- Pseudo Bayes Factor
 - States evidence in favor of competing models
 - May be unstable and require long MCMC chains